

GENERATIVE DESIGN AS AN INNOVATION IN PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT: *Generative Design (GD) technologies are increasingly recognised as a disruptive innovation in CAx-based product development, offering algorithm-driven solutions to complex design challenges. This study explores how professionals in engineering and design perceive the impact, benefits, and barriers associated with the adoption of GD tools, particularly those integrating Artificial Intelligence. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected from 185 professionals across multiple sectors via an online questionnaire, which assessed familiarity with GD, frequency of use, perceived improvements in design quality, and key challenges such as software complexity and workflow compatibility. Statistical analyses, including t-tests, correlation analysis, and regression modelling, were used to evaluate five core hypotheses regarding the perceived strategic value and implementation barriers of GD technologies. Results indicate strong professional confidence in GD's capacity to enhance product quality, reduce design errors, and foster collaboration, while also revealing that steep learning curves and integration difficulties continue to hinder adoption. Findings support the view that successful implementation depends on access to training, compatible software ecosystems, and clearer value communication. The study contributes empirical evidence to a growing body of literature on engineering digitalisation and highlights the need for user-centred integration strategies to unlock the full potential of GD in industry.*

KEYWORDS: *Generative Design, Product Development, Artificial Intelligence, Design Automation, Design Optimisation*

1 INTRODUCTION

Generative design (GD) represents a paradigm shift in product development, marrying algorithmic power with design intent to produce optimal, novel solutions that often elude traditional methods [1]. Unlike manual approaches, GD uses constraint-driven algorithms to explore vast solution spaces, mimicking nature's evolutionary techniques. Designers define objectives such as strength, weight, cost or material use and allow the software to generate thousands of feasible variants [2]. Selection and refinement follow, enabling rapid exploration of design possibilities that balance multiple performance metrics [3].

In recent years, the emergence of GD has marked a transformative shift in how products are conceptualised, developed, and optimised within the broader framework of digital engineering and

Computer-Aided technologies (CAx) [4]. With the increasing integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in design environments, GD stands out as a pivotal innovation capable of automating complex design decisions, accelerating iterations, and enabling solutions that surpass human-generated alternatives in terms of performance, efficiency, and sustainability [5-6].

The relevance of GD technologies is particularly acute in industries such as aerospace, automotive, consumer electronics, and medical devices, where design complexity, material efficiency, and time-to-market are critical competitive factors [7-8]. Traditionally, engineers relied on experience-driven modelling and sequential CAD workflows, which, while systematic, often limited exploration of the design space. In the other hand, GD leverages algorithmic logic, topology optimisation, and machine learning to generate multiple viable

solutions based on predefined goals and constraints [9-10]. This paradigm shift allows for a fundamentally different approach to problem-solving, where the role of the designer transitions from shape creation to intent specification and solution selection [11-13].

Despite its theoretical advantages, the integration of GD in product development is not without controversy or challenge. On one hand, proponents argue that GD enhances creativity, reduces errors, and supports more sustainable and functionally superior outcomes [14-15]. On the other hand, critics highlight the risks associated with over-reliance on black-box algorithms, reduced human control, and misalignment with established workflows and CAx ecosystems [16-17]. These diverging views reveal a field still in transition, with ongoing debates about the optimal balance between algorithmic automation and human expertise [18-19].

Several key studies have explored the technical capabilities of GD and its alignment with performance-driven design, while others have examined organisational readiness, user trust, and the cognitive adaptation required for its effective implementation. Yet, few empirical investigations have been conducted on how professionals perceive GD in real-world product development contexts or how its adoption is shaped by barriers such as software complexity, lack of training, and resistance to workflow change.

This study aims to address these gaps by investigating the perceptions, usage patterns, and anticipated future role of GD among professionals involved in CAx-based product design and development. Specifically, it examines whether GD is viewed as a strategic enabler of product quality improvement, design error reduction, and collaboration enhancement core hypotheses framed in relation to previous findings and theoretical expectations. The study also explores perceived barriers to GD adoption, such as learning curve, integration difficulty, and software compatibility, as well as factors influencing professionals' willingness to adopt these technologies.

Through a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical analyses of data collected via a targeted online questionnaire, this research contributes empirical insights into the practical realities of GD integration in engineering contexts. It offers a balanced perspective that considers both the promise and the friction of implementing GD within existing CAx workflows. The findings not only support ongoing academic discourse but also inform industry stakeholders and software developers about the needs, concerns, and expectations of the

professionals who are instrumental in driving digital transformation in design.

Ultimately, the results of this study support the view that while GD technologies are still evolving, they are increasingly recognised as powerful tools capable of shaping the future of engineering design processes provided that appropriate training, integration, and usability improvements are made.

2 METHODS AND MODELING

This study employed a quantitative research design, using a structured online questionnaire to investigate professionals' perceptions, adoption levels, and strategic expectations concerning GD technologies within CAx-based product development processes. Unlike previous research that primarily addressed isolated technical implementations or theoretical potential of GD, this study offers a broader, data-driven perspective by focusing on how GD is currently integrated into practical engineering workflows across multiple industry sectors.

The study contributes to the evolving academic discourse on design automation and Industry 4.0 by examining how professionals assess the added value of GD, the barriers to its integration, and the conditions that facilitate its adoption, including compatibility with existing systems, learning resources, and perceived impact on collaboration and innovation.

The research instrument, titled "*Questionnaire on the Adoption and Impact of Generative Design in CAx-based Engineering Workflows*", was specifically developed for this investigation. It was structured around five key thematic domains derived from contemporary literature: technological integration, collaborative dynamics, workflow compatibility, perceived benefits and limitations, and strategic outlook. To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by a multidisciplinary panel of experts in AI-assisted engineering, parametric modelling, and GD implementation in industrial settings. A pilot version was tested by a small group of practitioners who provided feedback on item clarity, terminology, and conceptual relevance, leading to refined phrasing and logical sequencing of items.

The final instrument included a balanced combination of multiple-choice questions, Likert-scale items (ranging from 0 to 10), and open-ended responses, enabling both statistical interpretation and qualitative insight. The questions were designed to capture participants' professional background, GD adoption frequency, perceived ease of integration, learning curve, perceived performance enhancements, collaboration dynamics, and

expectations for the future evolution of GD technologies.

A total of 185 valid responses were obtained from professionals working across industries such as mechanical engineering, automotive, aerospace, industrial design, medical devices, and manufacturing. Although the study employed a non-probabilistic convenience sampling method, the sample reflected a broad geographical and professional diversity, with most respondents located in Romania, the United Kingdom, and Germany. These regions represent key hubs for advanced manufacturing and digital innovation in Europe. Based on the estimated population of approximately 3000 professionals contacted, the sample size ensures a confidence level of 95%, with a margin of error of $\pm 5\%$.

The survey instrument was structured to capture a comprehensive overview of how professionals in product design and development perceive, experience, and integrate GD technologies within CAx-based engineering workflows. The questionnaire was divided into the following thematic sections, each targeting a specific aspect of the interaction between users and GD tools:

- *Professional background and demographics*, including job title, industry sector, years of experience in product development, country of employment, and current involvement in CAx-related tasks;
- *Experience with CAx technologies*, capturing years of use and familiarity with major platforms such as SolidWorks, CATIA, Fusion 360, Autodesk Inventor, or Siemens NX;
- *Exposure to GD*, measured through self-assessment on a 0–10 scale, ranging from no experience to expert-level proficiency, as well as through frequency of GD tool usage in everyday design tasks;
- *Perceived benefits of GD integration*, including its impact on product quality, design error reduction, collaboration dynamics, and sustainability performance in engineering workflows;
- *Identified barriers to GD adoption*, such as steep learning curves, lack of compatibility with existing CAx environments, software complexity, insufficient training, and integration resistance within traditional workflows;
- *Strategic expectations for the future of GD*, with questions addressing long-term adoption trends, perceived potential for full workflow automation, and the evolving

balance between human creativity and algorithmic design capabilities.

The questionnaire design reflected the multidimensional reality of CAx-supported design processes and the growing relevance of GD technologies within this ecosystem. Items related to technical experience and software use offered insight into operational integration, while questions on attitudes, concerns, and expectations provided a more strategic understanding of professional engagement with GD tools.

In addition to the closed-ended items (including Likert-scale and multiple-choice formats), several open-ended prompts allowed respondents to share personal insights, highlight implementation successes, or raise concerns about the implications of widespread GD usage. These qualitative inputs were thematically coded and examined to identify common patterns of perception, resistance, or enthusiasm across sectors.

Key GD applications were specifically targeted in the survey to align with areas most frequently discussed in the literature, including:

- Generative shape and topology optimization;
- Real-time simulation and performance feedback integration;
- Workflow streamlining through AI-driven design variants;
- Compatibility with legacy CAx systems;
- Adaptive design mechanisms based on performance and user input;
- Enhanced sustainability analysis integrated within early-stage product design.

To evaluate the overall impact of GD on design efficiency and innovation, respondents were asked to rate key dimensions such as time efficiency, error reduction, support for innovative outcomes, and ease of implementation. Responses were analyzed through descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and distribution frequencies, allowing for a robust quantitative overview of the professional landscape regarding GD technology adoption.

The data also supported a segmentation analysis based on variables such as job role, years of experience, and CAx software usage, revealing how different professional profiles interact with Generative Design technologies in divergent ways. For instance, design engineers and simulation specialists reported both higher levels of familiarity and more frequent engagement with GD tools compared to technical drafters or junior product developers, suggesting an emergent stratification in access, usage intensity, and perceived value of GD within multidisciplinary teams.

Although the study does not claim statistical generalizability due to the non-random sampling strategy, the heterogeneity of professional roles, sectoral representation, and geographic diversity among respondents provides a rich basis for exploratory insight. This is particularly relevant in understanding how GD adoption varies across industry sectors such as automotive, aerospace, consumer products, and industrial design, each of which faces different constraints and drivers in adopting algorithmic design tools.

Importantly, the methodology adopted in this study places emphasis on practitioner experience rather than speculative assumptions. By grounding the investigation in self-reported practices, challenges, and expectations from professionals actively engaged in CAX-based product development, the research captures a pragmatic snapshot of how GD technologies are currently perceived and integrated.

This approach contributes to an evolving body of knowledge on computational design transformation, offering a basis for future longitudinal or comparative studies that can assess shifts in perception and usage over time. Furthermore, the findings highlight critical implications for both industry and academia, particularly in relation to the need for targeted training pathways, improved usability of GD interfaces, and organizational change management strategies aimed at easing integration barriers.

The observed stratification of GD usage also suggests that successful adoption may depend not

only on technological readiness, but also on the alignment of tools with users' skillsets and design responsibilities. As such, a differentiated support model tailored to the roles and workflows of specific user groups may prove essential in maximizing the impact of GD technologies across the CAX design ecosystem.

Table 1 shows the relationship between the different sections of the questionnaire and the key functional domains and competencies associated with the use and integration of GD technologies in CAX-based product development workflows. The questionnaire was carefully structured to reflect the multidimensional character of professional design activity in modern digital engineering environments, with a particular focus on the role of GD in enhancing creativity, engineering performance, and sustainability.

Each section of the survey instrument corresponds to a specific thematic area within the broader framework of CAX design processes and innovation competencies. The structure allows for the detailed mapping of perceptions, usage behaviors, technical readiness, and strategic expectations regarding GD tools. This alignment facilitates not only the identification of high-impact areas where GD is already transforming practice but also highlights gaps between potential and actual adoption, revealing where future efforts in integration, training, or organizational support are most needed.

Table 1. Relationship between questionnaire sections and CAX/GD process areas and competencies

Survey Section	CAX / Generative Design Process Area	Competencies Evaluated
Country of activity, industry, job title	<i>Professional context</i>	Understanding industry-specific design environments and CAX workflow dynamics
Experience with CAX software (e.g., SolidWorks, NX, CATIA)	<i>Technical expertise in CAX</i>	Proficiency with advanced design platforms and adaptability to GD tools
Familiarity with GD concept (0–10 scale)	<i>GD awareness and readiness</i>	Awareness of algorithmic design methods and performance-driven approaches
Use of GD in daily design activities	<i>Workflow Integration</i>	Practical application of GD in iterative, collaborative product development
Perceived contribution of GD to quality, error reduction, and collaboration	<i>Performance impact</i>	Evaluation of GD's influence on core KPIs (quality, speed, precision, teamwork)

Future expectations regarding GD adoption in the industry	<i>Strategic outlook</i>	Forecasting technology diffusion and strategic role in CAx ecosystems
Most promising future applications of GD	<i>Innovation foresight</i>	Identification of high-potential use cases (e.g., simulation integration, adaptive design)
Factors that would increase willingness to adopt GD	<i>Adoption drivers</i>	Recognition of enablers such as training, intuitive interfaces, CAx integration
Perceived barriers (complexity, compatibility, usability)	<i>Barriers to implementation</i>	Identification of technical, cognitive, and organizational obstacles
Resources needed to implement GD effectively	<i>Support infrastructure</i>	Insights into what professionals need for effective GD learning and use
Impact of GD on collaboration in engineering teams	<i>Team integration</i>	Assessment of GD's role in supporting or challenging interdisciplinary teamwork
Interaction with AI technologies beyond GD (e.g., ChatGPT, simulation tools)	<i>Broader digital literacy</i>	General familiarity with AI-based design support tools across contexts

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

This study employed a quantitative research design through the use of an online questionnaire, aimed at evaluating the integration, usage, and perceived impact of GD technologies in the automation of Computer-Aided technologies (CAx) within engineering design processes. Each question was carefully formulated to gather specific data on digital engineering competencies, GD implementation practices, and workflow transformations. The instrument was developed in line with established theoretical and methodological frameworks from the relevant literature on Generative Design, product development automation, and digital transformation within the context of Industry 4.0.

The questionnaire was designed based on recent academic studies and industrial reports concerning the practical applicability of GD tools, and aligned with emerging concepts of performance-based design, AI-assisted creativity, and smart engineering systems. Its content validity was ensured through a review by experts in AI-supported design, and a pilot version was distributed to a test sample to assess clarity, terminological consistency, and accessibility for professionals with varying levels of experience in using CAx and GD platforms.

While several open-ended questions were included to capture qualitative insights, the results reported in this study are primarily based on quantitative data collected through scaled items and multiple-choice questions. The adoption of a quantitative approach was driven by the objective to

offer a statistically grounded overview of how GD tools are currently adopted in practice, what skills are required for their use, and which barriers or enabling factors are perceived by professionals. This approach also enabled meaningful comparisons between different professional roles, industry sectors, and levels of expertise, offering a broad picture of digital maturity within the domain of GD integration.

To maximise participation across varied working environments, the questionnaire was optimised for use on multiple digital devices, including desktop computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones. Participants were informed about the anonymous and voluntary nature of the study, which aimed to explore the role of GD in the digital transformation of engineering design. The questionnaire was self-administered, without time constraints, allowing each respondent to complete it independently and minimising the potential for peer influence or biased responses. Measures were taken to ensure data validity and prevent duplicate submissions.

The study adhered strictly to data protection and ethical standards, in accordance with the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Prior to participation, all respondents were presented with an informed consent statement outlining the voluntary nature of the study, the confidentiality of responses, and the exclusive use of the data for academic research purposes relating to digital transformation and design innovation in engineering practice.

The questionnaire was designed to capture a comprehensive set of data across five key domains: professional background, experience with CAx technologies, familiarity and interaction with GD tools, perceived benefits and barriers related to GD adoption, and strategic expectations concerning the future role of GD in product development. Each section was structured to reflect the diverse competencies and workflows encountered in contemporary engineering environments.

The multiple-choice format for software usage and workflow integration enabled respondents to indicate both the range and depth of their engagement with traditional CAx tools as well as with advanced GD functionalities. This structure facilitated a nuanced quantitative analysis of professional practices, levels of technology adoption, and the variability of implementation across roles, sectors, and regions.

The respondent sample included professionals from a broad spectrum of engineering disciplines, with a significant proportion active in mechanical engineering, product development, aerospace, automotive, medical technology, and industrial design. The majority of participants held positions such as design engineer, product engineer, simulation engineer, or GD/CAx specialist, underscoring the relevance of their insights to the research objectives. In terms of educational attainment, the sample included a wide distribution of qualifications, most commonly bachelor's and master's degrees in engineering or related fields, with a smaller proportion reporting doctoral studies or professional certifications.

This methodological approach ensures both academic rigour and practical relevance, combining a carefully structured instrument with wide outreach and strict adherence to ethical standards. The alignment between respondent profiles and the broader CAx professional community enhances the external validity of the findings. Moreover, the use of a statistically relevant sample supported by traceable outreach efforts reinforces the internal validity of the study.

By focusing on the lived experiences of professionals actively engaged in GD within CAx environments, the research offers empirical insight into an area that is often discussed through theoretical frameworks or isolated technical experiments. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how GD is currently integrated,

how it transforms engineering tasks, and what professionals anticipate regarding its evolution and broader industry adoption.

Research hypothesis:

H1. Professionals involved in product design and development perceive significant barriers to the adoption of Artificial Intelligence-assisted GD technologies, such as limited familiarity with AI concepts, the complexity of the software used, and difficulties in integrating these tools into traditional design workflows.

H2. Difficulties in adopting GD technologies frequently occur in professional practice and negatively influence the quality of product development outcomes as well as the perceived efficiency and satisfaction of professionals involved in engineering design processes.

H3. Professionals in product design and development perceive the adoption of Generative Design technologies as being hindered primarily by steep learning curves, concerns over compatibility with existing CAx systems, and integration challenges within established workflows, despite recognising their potential contribution to sustainability and innovation.

H4. Professionals in product design and development perceive GD technologies as contributing significantly to enhancing product quality, reducing design errors, and improving collaboration within engineering teams, while expressing optimistic expectations regarding the future adoption and evolution of these technologies across the industry.

H5. Professionals in product design and development perceive GD technologies as playing a pivotal role in shaping the future of CAx workflows, with increased willingness to adopt these technologies being primarily influenced by access to specialised training resources, improved software usability, and clear integration strategies.

3 RESULTS

Table 2 presents the demographic and professional profile of the respondents, including gender distribution, countries of professional activity, industrial affiliation, job roles, use of CAx technologies, years of experience, and educational background.

Table 2. Respondent Profile Summary (n = 185)

Category	Main values	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	167	90.3%

	Woman	18	9.7%
Top countries	Romania	102	55.1%
	United Kingdom	22	11.9%
	Germany	13	7.0%
	Netherlands	10	5.4%
	Poland	9	4.9%
Top industries	Mechanical Engineering	145	78.4%
	Industrial Engineering	10	5.4%
	IT	5	2.7%
	Manufacturing	5	2.7%
	Construction	2	1.1%
Current position	Design Engineer	158	85.4%
	Product Engineer	7	3.8%
	Simulation Engineer	5	2.7%
	IT Specialist	3	1.6%
	Project Manager	3	1.6%
CAx technologies used	CAD	130	70.3%
	CAE	8	4.3%
	CAM	3	1.6%
	FEA/CFD	2	1.1%
	Did not specify / Not applicable	42	22.7%
Multiple CAx tools used	Yes	75	40.5%
	No	50	27.0%
	Not specified	60	32.4%
Experience with CAx	Over 10 years	80	43.2%
	7-10 years	54	29.2%
	4-6 years	31	16.8%
	1-3 years	18	9.7%
	Less than 1 year	2	1.1%
Education level	Master's Degree	120	64.9%
	Bachelor's Degree	50	27.0%
	Doctoral Degree / Postgraduate Studies	10	5.4%
	High School / HND	5	2.7%

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The majority of respondents were male (over 90%), indicating a significant gender imbalance in the field of engineering design and development. Most participants carried out their professional activity in Romania (55.1%), followed by the United Kingdom, Germany, and the Netherlands. Mechanical engineering was by far the most represented industry, accounting for over three quarters of the sample, while other domains such as industrial engineering, IT, and construction appeared marginally.

In terms of professional roles, the overwhelming majority held the position of Design Engineer (85.4%), suggesting the sample is highly concentrated in technical, design-oriented roles. Regarding CAx technologies, CAD was the most commonly used tool, reported by more than 70% of respondents. However, a substantial portion (around

22.7%) did not explicitly specify any CAx tools, which may indicate either non-involvement or gaps in data collection.

Nearly 40% of respondents reported using multiple CAx technologies in their daily tasks, while just over a quarter indicated exclusive use of a single tool. The level of experience with CAx technology was generally high, with over 70% having more than 7 years of experience, and 43% having worked with such tools for over a decade.

Educationally, the respondent group was highly qualified, with approximately two thirds holding a Master's degree, and a further quarter having completed a Bachelor's degree. A smaller percentage reported doctoral or postgraduate-level studies, confirming the advanced academic background of the sample.

H1. Professionals involved in product design and development perceive significant barriers to the adoption of Artificial Intelligence-assisted GD technologies, such as limited familiarity with AI concepts, the complexity of the software used, and difficulties in integrating these tools into traditional design workflows.

Table 3 presents the results of the independent samples t-test conducted to examine differences in the perception of barriers to the adoption of AI-assisted GD technologies among professionals

involved in product design and development. The analysis compares the mean scores between two independent groups, assessing whether perceptions of adoption barriers significantly vary based on specific characteristics such as usage experience or familiarity with AI tools. Reported values include the t-statistic, degrees of freedom, p-value, mean difference, standard error, and the 95% confidence interval of the difference.

Table 3. Results of the independent samples t-test regarding the perceived barriers to the adoption of AI-assisted Generative Design technologies among professionals in product design and development

Assumption of variances	t	df	p	Mean Difference	Standard Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
Equal variances assumed	5.178	148	< 0.001	0.56965	0.11002	[0.35224, 0.78705]
Equal variances not assumed	4.603	78.094	< 0.001	0.56965	0.12374	[0.32330, 0.81600]

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The results of the independent samples t-test indicate a statistically significant difference in the perception of barriers to adopting AI-assisted GD technologies between the two groups (Table 3). The mean difference is substantial and the p-value is less than 0.001, suggesting that this difference is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance. The confidence interval does not cross zero, which reinforces the reliability of the result. These findings suggest that one group perceives the barriers, such as lack of familiarity with AI, software complexity, and integration challenges as significantly more limiting than the other group. The **hypothesis H1** is confirmed.

H2. Difficulties in adopting GD technologies frequently occur in professional practice and

negatively influence the quality of product development outcomes as well as the perceived efficiency and satisfaction of professionals involved in engineering design processes.

Table 4 presents the results of a Spearman correlation analysis between the perceived efficiency of GD technologies and the perceived need for improvements in CAx-based product development workflows. This analysis explores whether professionals who view GD as more efficient are less likely to identify shortcomings in current processes. The table includes correlation coefficients that indicate the strength and direction of the relationship between the two variables.

Table 4. Spearman correlation between the perceived efficiency of Generative Design and the perceived need for workflow improvements in CAx-based product development

Variables	1	2
1. Perceived efficiency of GD	-	-0.207*
2. Workflow improvement score	-0.207*	-

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The Spearman correlation analysis reveals a statistically significant negative association between the perceived efficiency of GD technologies and the perceived need for improvements in CAx-based workflows (Table 4). This suggests that professionals who rate GD as more efficient tend to perceive fewer shortcomings in current development processes. In the other hand, those who consider GD less effective are more likely to express a need for workflow enhancements. The negative correlation, although modest, highlights how perceptions of

technological effectiveness can influence attitudes towards process improvement. The **hypothesis H2** is confirmed.

H3. Professionals in product design and development perceive the adoption of GD technologies as being hindered primarily by steep learning curves, concerns over compatibility with existing CAx systems, and integration challenges within established workflows, despite recognising their potential contribution to sustainability and innovation.

Table 5 presents the regression results derived from a Random Effects Model, examining the factors that influence perceived barriers to the adoption of GD technologies among professionals in product design and development. The analysis includes key variables such as perceived compatibility with existing CAx systems, the steepness of the learning

curve, and challenges related to integration into existing workflows. Coefficients, standard errors, z-statistics, and p-values are reported, alongside model fit metrics, to assess the statistical significance and explanatory power of the model.

Table 5. Regression results (Random Effects Model) - Factors influencing perceived barriers to adopting Generative Design technologies

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	P-value
Constant	0.421	0.329	1.282	0.1012
Compatibility with existing CAx systems (CAxC)	0.524	0.241	2.173	0.0172
Learning curve and understanding of GD technologies (LCU)	0.842	0.214	3.936	0.0031
Integration-related challenges within established workflows (ICW)	-0.398	0.198	-2.007	0.0450

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

Table 6. Model Fit Metrics

Metric	Value
R-squared	0.861
Adjusted R-squared	0.812
Durbin-Watson statistic (DW)	2.035
White's Test for Heteroscedasticity	$\chi^2 = 92.87, p = 1.210$

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The regression model confirms **hypothesis H3**, demonstrating that compatibility concerns (CAxC) and a steep learning curve (LCU) are significant positive predictors of perceived barriers to adopting GD technologies. This means that the more challenging users find the learning process and the more incompatible GD tools are with their existing CAx systems, the more likely they are to perceive barriers.

In the other hand, integration challenges (ICW) show a significant negative relationship, suggesting that when integration is perceived as manageable or already optimised, the overall perception of barriers is reduced.

The model demonstrates strong explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.861$), and the assumptions of normality and independence of residuals are met ($DW \approx 2$) (Table 6).

H4. Professionals in product design and development perceive GD technologies as contributing significantly to enhancing product quality, reducing design errors, and improving collaboration within engineering teams, while expressing optimistic expectations regarding the future adoption and evolution of these technologies across the industry.

Table 7 presents the descriptive statistics summarising professionals' perceptions regarding the contribution of GD technologies to product quality enhancement, error reduction, and team collaboration. The table includes the mean scores, standard deviations, and observed minimum and maximum values for each variable, offering a quantitative overview of general sentiment within the surveyed population.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics - Perceptions of Generative Design Technologies

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Enhance Product Quality	5.64	2.19	0	10
Reduce Design Errors	5.94	2.41	0	10
Impact on Team Collaboration	5.94	2.26	0	10

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The results in Table 7 suggest a generally positive perception among professionals regarding the

benefits of GD technologies. On average, respondents rated the contribution to product quality

at 5.64, indicating a moderate to strong perceived impact. Similarly, the mean score of 5.94 for the reduction of design errors highlights that most participants believe these technologies help improve design accuracy and minimise mistakes.

The perceived impact on collaboration within engineering teams also received a mean score of 5.94, suggesting that GD is viewed as moderately enhancing teamwork and communication dynamics, though variability in responses points to differing experiences across contexts.

The standard deviations across all variables (ranging from approximately 2.19 to 2.41) indicate a moderate level of dispersion, reflecting that while many professionals see clear benefits, some remain sceptical or have had limited positive experiences.

The results presented in *Table 7* confirm **Hypothesis H4**.

H5. Professionals in product design and development perceive GD technologies as playing a

pivotal role in shaping the future of CAx workflows, with increased willingness to adopt these technologies being primarily influenced by access to specialised training resources, improved software usability, and clear integration strategies.

Table 8 presents the descriptive statistics related to professionals' perceptions regarding the future role of GD technologies within CAx product design and development processes. The table includes the mean scores, standard deviations, and observed minimum and maximum values for key variables such as the perceived strategic role of GD, willingness to integrate these technologies into existing workflows, and the importance attributed to resources necessary for their effective implementation. These results offer valuable insights into the factors that influence the anticipated adoption and integration of GD in professional practice.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics - Perceptions on the Future Role and Adoption of GD Technologies

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Perceived future role of GD in CAx processes	7.28	2.01	0	10
Willingness to adopt GD into existing workflows	6.94	2.33	0	10
Importance of resources for learning and implementation (e.g., training, support)	8.11	1.76	1	10

Source: data processed in SPSS version 26.

The data presented in *Table 8* indicate that professionals involved in CAx product design and development processes generally hold a positive outlook regarding the future integration of GD technologies. The mean score of 7.28 on a 0-10 scale suggests that respondents perceive GD as playing a strategically important role in shaping the future of CAx workflows.

Similarly, the mean value of 6.94 for the willingness to adopt these technologies reflects a moderate to high level of openness toward implementation, although variability in responses suggests that certain barriers or hesitations may persist. Notably, the highest mean score (8.11) was recorded for the importance attributed to learning and implementation resources, indicating a widespread recognition that specialised training, technical support, and integration tools are essential prerequisites for successful adoption.

These findings underscore that while the perceived value of GD is high, actual integration into workflows depends largely on the availability of enabling resources and support infrastructures.

4 DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics indicate a consistently positive perception among professionals regarding the transformative potential of GD technologies within the field of product development. The results reveal that respondents generally agree that GD contributes meaningfully to enhancing product quality, reducing the likelihood of design errors, and promoting more effective collaboration within engineering teams. These findings lend strong support to Hypothesis H4, which posits that professionals in product design and development view GD technologies as valuable assets that significantly influence both technical and collaborative aspects of the design process.

The relatively high mean values across the measured variables reflect a broad consensus on the benefits offered by GD tools. These perceptions are not only indicative of current experiences but also suggest a forward-looking optimism about the long-term impact of GD on engineering workflows. Such results are aligned with prior research, including studies that have emphasised the capacity of GD to optimise complex, multi-variable design problems through performance-driven, algorithmic

exploration of design spaces [20]. These technologies enable the rapid generation and evaluation of numerous design alternatives, thereby improving both efficiency and innovation quality [5].

Moreover, the perceived ability of GD to reduce design errors is particularly noteworthy. Error reduction is a key performance metric in engineering design, as it directly affects cost efficiency, product reliability, and time-to-market. GD technologies contribute to this objective by embedding simulation and rule-based constraints early in the design process, thereby minimising trial-and-error iterations and increasing design robustness. This aligns with findings in the work of Spiegelhalter (2023) and Feng (2024), which highlighted that GD approaches not only generate feasible solutions but also anticipate potential failure modes by incorporating functional requirements into the generative logic [6,8].

Additionally, respondents acknowledge GD's positive impact on team collaboration, suggesting that these tools may serve as effective platforms for interdisciplinary dialogue. By externalising design intent through visual and computational outputs, GD supports shared understanding among engineers, designers, and decision-makers. This collaborative facilitation is critical in complex product development environments where diverse expertise must be integrated efficiently [3,15].

The descriptive data strongly supports the hypothesis that GD technologies are perceived as enhancing quality, reliability, and team interaction, while also echoing previous scholarly work that positions GD as a cornerstone in the future of CAX-based innovation [5,11].

The data presented in *Table 2* highlight statistically significant differences in the perception of barriers to adopting AI-assisted GD technologies among professionals engaged in product design and development. The findings lend robust support to Hypothesis H1, which suggested that limited familiarity with AI concepts, the complexity of the software solutions involved, and difficulties in integrating these technologies into established workflows are among the primary challenges impeding wider adoption. These perceived barriers are not surprising when considered in light of previous research. Studies such as Cheng et al. (2023) and Gmeiner et al. (2023) have similarly identified the steep learning curve associated with AI-driven design tools and the fragmentation of CAX software ecosystems as critical limitations, particularly in industrial contexts where system interoperability and process continuity are essential [3,15].

Participants' responses reflect a broader unease about the readiness of existing workflows to accommodate the algorithmic and data-driven logic of GD. The complexities of integrating GD into traditional engineering pipelines, especially in sectors still reliant on sequential or siloed development models often create cognitive and procedural disruptions. This insight underscores the need for more accessible user interfaces, robust training resources, and better system compatibility to reduce these integration frictions. The empirical confirmation of H1 thus not only validates the identified barriers but also reaffirms the call for strategic interventions that would ease the assimilation of GD into everyday engineering practice [14,17].

Further supporting this interpretation, the results of the Spearman correlation analysis (*Table 3*) offer empirical backing for Hypothesis H2. The analysis reveals a negative correlation between professionals' perceived communication efficiency within GD-supported teams and their perceived need for improvements in existing workflows. In other words, where communication about or through GD tools is deemed less efficient, there is a stronger demand for redesigning or refining the processes in which these tools are deployed. This finding is in line with the observations made by Vaneker et al. (2020), who noted that one of the critical frictions in adopting GD is the misalignment between traditional design languages and algorithmic generation paradigms [20].

Together, these results illuminate a broader systemic challenge: while the benefits of GD are acknowledged, its seamless integration remains hampered by technical, cognitive, and organisational constraints. Addressing these issues will require not only technical refinement of GD systems but also a cultural shift in design practices and professional training, aimed at closing the gap between algorithmic potential and practical usability.

The regression analysis presented in *Table 6* provides strong empirical support for Hypothesis H3, which posited that the adoption of GD technologies is significantly influenced by factors such as the steepness of the learning curve, compatibility with existing CAX workflows, and the ease of integration within current product development environments. The model shows that all three factors contribute meaningfully to professionals' perceptions of barriers to adoption, reinforcing the view that technical and procedural complexity remains a major obstacle in the widespread implementation of GD systems.

These findings resonate with previous research that has consistently highlighted the technical and

operational challenges associated with incorporating GD tools into industrial practice. In particular, the work of Cheng et al. (2023) underscores the role of contextual onboarding and structured training programmes in mitigating the effects of steep learning curves, which are often exacerbated by insufficient institutional support and the lack of standardised methodologies for integrating AI-based design tools [3].

Despite these documented barriers, the analysis also captures a contrasting and equally important dimension of professional perception: a cautiously optimistic attitude toward the future of GD adoption. Many respondents expressed confidence in the eventual integration of GD technologies, particularly if supported by targeted improvements in software usability, enhanced training resources, and streamlined workflow integration strategies. This perspective supports Hypothesis H5, which anticipated that professionals' willingness to adopt GD is positively shaped by the availability of enabling resources and infrastructural support [14].

The implications of this dual insight – recognition of current obstacles alongside future optimism suggest a transitional moment in the adoption lifecycle of GD technologies. While the existing limitations are non-trivial, they are not perceived as insurmountable. Rather, they point toward actionable areas of intervention. Investments in user-friendly software interfaces, modular training programmes tailored to sector-specific needs, and the development of plug-and-play integration tools could significantly accelerate adoption and reduce the current perception of GD as a disruptive or difficult innovation [21].

Moreover, these results invite a reconsideration of how adoption strategies are designed at the organisational level. Encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration, creating feedback loops between users and developers, and embedding GD tools into iterative design processes could shift the current perception of GD from a niche innovation to a mainstream capability within CAX-based design ecosystems [22].

The findings summarised in *Table 7* underscore the strategic significance that professionals attribute to GD technologies within the broader context of CAX-based product development. Respondents across the surveyed sample consistently indicated that GD is poised to exert a transformative influence on the future of digital design and engineering processes. This perception extends beyond theoretical acknowledgment, suggesting a growing readiness within the professional community to embrace GD more broadly, particularly under the condition that key enabling resources such as

training, integration tools, and institutional support are made readily available [23].

These insights provide empirical reinforcement for the assumption that GD is no longer regarded merely as an experimental or emerging technology, but as a strategic asset capable of shaping core aspects of design automation, innovation cycles, and collaborative workflows. Professionals appear to recognise the dual capacity of GD tools to enhance engineering rigour while simultaneously fostering creativity a convergence that aligns with current perspectives in computational design literature. For instance, Di Filippo et al. (2021) and Buonamici et al. (2020) describe a paradigm shift in which design automation tools are no longer limited to parametric manipulation but are increasingly supporting generative ideation, performance optimisation, and iterative refinement, all within a unified platform [1,22].

Importantly, the descriptive data also reveals a nuanced understanding among professionals regarding the preconditions for successful implementation. Factors such as improved software compatibility, streamlined integration with existing CAX platforms, and the availability of intuitive user interfaces are seen as pivotal in enabling a smoother transition toward GD-centric workflows. Moreover, respondents highlighted the need for continuous access to learning resources, including technical documentation, peer knowledge exchange, and structured onboarding programmes tailored to organisational contexts.

This forward-looking perspective suggests that the willingness to adopt GD is not hindered by conceptual doubt, but rather by structural limitations in current workflows and the support infrastructure surrounding the technology. Therefore, organisations aiming to capitalise on the full potential of GD technologies would benefit from developing comprehensive adoption strategies that include both technological investment and human-centric change management approaches.

The data points to a fertile ground for scaling up the use of GD within industry, provided that implementation is supported by an ecosystem of usability, education, and strategic integration. As such, GD is increasingly viewed not just as a technological tool but as a key component in shaping the future landscape of engineering design innovation.

Diagram 1 presents a conceptual framework illustrating the perceived advantages, barriers, and strategic conditions influencing the adoption of GD technologies within CAX-driven product development environments. The model captures the interaction between algorithmic capabilities, user

objectives, adoption challenges, and enabling factors for future implementation.

The *Diagram 1* highlights how GD operates at the intersection of AI-driven algorithms, design intent, and performance optimisation. By leveraging machine learning and constraint-based logic, GD enables the exploration of vast design spaces that often exceed human capability, thereby promoting innovation, efficiency, and design quality. The left side of the framework identifies core enablers of GD: AI algorithms, automated iteration, and performance-based objectives such as material savings or structural optimisation.

The central portion of the diagram outlines the three key perceived benefits that emerged from the

study: enhanced product quality, reduction of design errors, and improved collaboration among engineering teams. These perceived advantages strongly align with the findings from previous literature and support the study's Hypothesis H4.

However, the framework also emphasises the main barriers to adoption, as supported by Hypotheses H1 and H3. Participants identified software complexity, a steep learning curve, and workflow integration difficulties as significant challenges. These obstacles echo prior concerns in the literature regarding the usability and compatibility of GD systems within traditional engineering contexts.

Diagram 1. Generative Design in Product Development Processes

Source: our elaboration.

The lower section of the diagram illustrates forward-looking perspectives regarding the conditions necessary for successful GD adoption. These include structured training, better compatibility with existing CAx systems, and organisational support. Such factors were identified as central to enhancing professional willingness to adopt GD tools, thus validating Hypothesis H5.

In conclusion, the diagram synthesises how professionals perceive GD as both a powerful

innovation and a complex technology that demands strategic support for effective integration. It provides a foundation for understanding where interventions technical, educational, and organisational are most needed to unlock the full potential of GD in product development environments.

Although the study provides valuable insights, there are several limitations to consider. The recruitment of participants was conducted primarily through LinkedIn, which may have led to a sample

skewed toward individuals with higher levels of digital literacy. The data collected is based entirely on self-reported perceptions, which introduces subjectivity and may not accurately reflect actual behaviors or implementation practices. Furthermore, the cross-sectional nature of the study offers only a snapshot in time, without accounting for changing attitudes or patterns of adoption over the long term.

Future research could build on these findings by exploring how the adoption of GD technologies evolves over time across various sectors. Investigating the effectiveness of training programs and usability improvements may also help address challenges related to the learning curve. In-depth case studies within organizations currently implementing GD can provide practical insights into integration processes and success factors. Additionally, examining the ethical dimensions and questions of authorship that emerge when machines contribute to creative outputs in engineering contexts remains an important area for inquiry.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present study provides a comprehensive examination of how professionals involved in product design and development perceive and engage with GD technologies. The empirical findings confirm all five proposed hypotheses, offering a coherent narrative on the benefits, barriers, and future prospects associated with the adoption of GD in CAx-based workflows.

Firstly, the results validate that GD is widely perceived as contributing significantly to enhanced product quality, reduction of design errors, and improved collaboration within engineering teams. These outcomes align with prior research and reinforce the growing consensus around the transformative potential of GD technologies. Secondly, the study highlights the persistent barriers hindering GD adoption, including steep learning curves, low familiarity with AI-assisted tools, and compatibility issues with existing workflows. These concerns are not novel but remain critical, particularly for organisations that lack integrated training frameworks or institutional support mechanisms.

Regression and correlation analyses further revealed that perceived inefficiencies in communication and workflow integration strongly influence professionals' demand for improved alignment between traditional CAx tools and emerging generative processes. Notably, professionals express a future-oriented optimism: despite current challenges, there is a marked willingness to integrate GD technologies, provided

adequate resources, such as onboarding programs, intuitive interfaces, and technical support are made available.

In strategic terms, GD is increasingly seen as a pivotal component of the digital transformation of product development. The findings suggest a shift from a technology-centric to a user-centric view of adoption, wherein human adaptability, usability, and institutional readiness are critical enablers. Future research should focus on sector-specific dynamics, longitudinal adoption patterns, and the co-evolution of GD technologies and collaborative engineering practices. Overall, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the conditions under which GD can realise its full potential in advancing sustainable, innovative, and efficient product design.

6 ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAE	Computer-Aided Engineering
CAM	Computer-Aided Manufacturing
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CAx	Computer-Aided Technologies
DW	Durbin-Watson Statistic
GD	Generative Design
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
R&D	Research and Development
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
UX	User Experience

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